

RESEARCH TREND BRAIN GYM EFFECT ON EDUCATION: A BIBLIOMETRIC REVIEW AND ANALYSIS

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Abstract

This article was written to analyze research trends of brain gym's effect on education in the last five years, 2018 - 2023. The method used is Bibliometric analysis, assisted by the VOSviewer application. The object of study is the title and abstract of 94 articles from international journals indexed by Scopus in the last five years. The data was obtained using the keyword "brain gym in education." The results show the network, overlay, and density between parts. Only a few nations have researched the brain gym in scientific education. Thus, based on the findings of this bibliometric study, present an overview and suggestions for future research.

Keywords: Bibliometric, Brain Gym, Education

1. INTRODUCTION

The 21st-century learning is aimed at preparing 21st-century generations to adapt to the newest technology changes. This learning seeks to prepare people to adapt and continually adjust to the numerous changes that occur to deal successfully in the future. The application of 21st-century learning is an essential problem in the implementation of education in Indonesia. These objectives incorporate literacy, knowledge prowess, skills and attitudes, and mastery of technology. The learning problems of the twenty-first century need the younger generation to possess diverse abilities that will help them navigate life in the current day. These 21st-century abilities help learners become more attentive to the changing times. To have strong skills, learners must have a solid knowledge basis and an understanding of lifelong learning. The goal of 21st-century skills is for everyone to master the 4C, which are the abilities that learners must have to adapt and survive in the current period of Industrial Revolution 4.0. The four C's are communication, collaboration, critical thinking and problem-solving, and creativity and innovation. 4C is a soft talent that will be considerably more valuable than learning hard skills.

High-quality human resources with a wide range of talents are in high demand in today's world, yet the skills of certain Indonesian students remain relatively poor. According to the OECD's PISA ratings as of December 3, 2019, the critical thinking abilities of students at various educational levels nationally remain inadequate. The reading literacy score was 72 out of 77, math 72 out of 78, and science 70th out of 78 nations. The

pupils' ability to retain the subject information was regarded as high, but they lacked argumentation and critical thinking skills. In other words, pupils in Indonesia excel in memorizing issues but struggle with application and reasoning. Some of the research questions used in this study are (i) How is the distribution of the publications in the field of brain gym? (ii) What are the primary publications and research interests based on the author keywords in brain gym?

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Brain Gym is a collection of basic movement exercises designed to help students learn and adjust to daily pressures. This approach was created by Paul E. Dennison, Dr. Phill, and his wife Gail E. Dennison. The brain gym movement was originally meant for adults, but by the year 2000, it had expanded to include children and newborns. Light gymnastic motions are used in brain workouts, such as exercising the hands and feet, to offer stimulation to the brain. This stimulation can boost cognitive capacities such as alertness, focus, and speed of learning, as well as memory, problem-solving, and creativity (Muhammad, 2011). According to Dennison (2003), the following brain exercises include many movements. Brain gym closely attached to life is also used in the health and social fields (Abduh, 2018: Azizah, 2017: Ginting, 2019: Gunawati, 2020).

The brain fully develops between the ages of 20 and 40 (according to a study of 10,000 individuals), since before the age of 20, a person often lives a school life that focuses on the school curriculum, and therefore only specific portions of the brain are actively employed. (Kato, 2016) So it is critical that we are able to boost all brain processes throughout this time period. According to diverse studies, practices, and applications conducted by various organizations, brain workouts give integrated motions that are easy and enjoyable. Brain exercise can also improve mental health by increasing the workload of the two hemispheres of the brain. (Heni, 2021: Kulkarni, 2019: Pramesti, 2018: Purwanti, 2019: Rianti, 2021, Suwardiyanto, 2021).

The brain functions to control all body functions, brain exercises utilize and form a relationship between the brain and the body, by carrying out movements to access the brain, it turns out that we can integrate all related areas in the learning process so that we can increase our ability to maximize both sides. Both hemispheres must be active at the same time in order for both to operate successfully. One of the hemispheres will be turned off, which will result in a variety of difficulties.

Humans' conscious mind has a potential capacity of just 12% of their brain, and a genius can optimize 5-6% of their conscious brain capacity, or less than half, with the remaining 88% being subconscious potential capacity (Laksana, 2017). The brain is constantly linked to an individual's intellect or intelligence. The brain is also the control center for the mental and bodily systems, allowing them to perform several functions at once. You may boost your thinking abilities by sitting up straight, having excellent social interactions, laughing, eating fruit, reading, and, most importantly, exercising.

3. METHODOLOGY

This study employed bibliometric analysis to present an overview of the research areas into which publications, authors, and journals may be divided. The Scopus database was used to conduct a literature and metadata search that began in June 2018 with the term "Brain Gym and Education," yielding 413 papers. The findings are checked to ensure that just the necessary data is received. Screening is done by restricting the publication time of publications throughout the previous six years (2018-2023). The search results for the document are then exported to RIS format. The units were examined using the VOS viewer, a bibliometric tool that displays the network of authors, affiliates, nations, and keywords. The previous report provides detailed information on how to use VOSviewer. Keyword analysis and the article title were utilized to identify groupings and topics for study using Scopus sources in six categories. The database comprises 94 publications about the brain gym in scientific education, including 69 articles, 13 conference papers, 8 book chapters, two reviews, one book, and one erratum. In this study, sample articles downloaded in *CSV format from Scopus are analyzed using VOS viewer software to help visualize and discover patterns.

4. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The smallest number of terms used in the studied research according to Scopus. After being analyzed there are 7 categories, they are by year, countries, affiliation, author, type, subject area, and funding sponsor (see Fig. 1).

Documents by year

Fig. 1. Papers regarding Brain Gym on education published in five years

Counting papers by countries for keywords of “brain gym” in education, there are 24 countries having publications about brain gym in science education. The countries are United States, Indonesia, United Kingdom, Germany, India, China, Canada, Japan, Russian Federation, Spain, Iran, Thailand, Denmark, Malaysia, Peru, Ecuador, Egypt, France, Israel, Italy, Mexico, Portugal, Slovenia and Taiwan.. The US is the country that publishes the most paper discussing the brain gym in education (19 papers). The second country has 17 papers from Indonesia, and then United Kingdom has 9 papers. This opportunity is linked to research about brain gym in science education. This statement came with results from the VOS viewer 1.6.18 program, file CSV. Each cluster is divided as follows: the first cluster has 14 things, the second cluster has 9 items, and the third cluster has 7 items. The colors are red, green, and blue. The United States has published the most articles on brain gym in scientific education, and they have collaborated with other nations. Table 1 shows the top ten nations for brain gym in scientific education research, but just the top 10.

Table 1. Top ten countries/regions for brain gym in science education research

Country/Region	Freq.
United States	18
Indonesia	17
United Kingdom	9
Germany	7
India	7
China	6
Canada	5
Japan	5
Russian Federation	5
Spain	5

Documents by subject area

Fig. 2. Visualization country using VOS viewer using network visualization.

Analysis data from Scopus (see Fig. 2) closely related to brain gym in medicine (27.7%), computer science (14%), social science (9%), Neuroscience (9%), Health Professions (7.7%), Nursing (5.2%), Psychology (5.2%), Biochemistry, Genetics, Molecular Biology and Engineering (4.5%) and other subject areas (14.8%). However, brain gyms in scientific education are still restricted to design, and there is a dearth of research on classroom application. This is an excellent chance to study brain gym learning in science education. This finding also demonstrates the efficacy of bibliometric analysis in successfully investigating and visualizing the present literature, which can be utilized to determine if more study should be conducted.

Table 2. The number of publications about brain gym in science education

By type	Frequency
Article	69
Conference paper	13
Book Chapter	8
Review	2
Book	1
Erratum	1

Documents by type

Fig. 3. Publications based on documents by type issued.

Fig. 4. Visualization topic area using VOS viewer

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